

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF FORMATION OF SYSTEMIC KNOWLEDGE OF CHEMISTRY IN SECONDARY SCHOOL

Parakhnenko V.,

Ph.D. Lecturer-trainee, Department of chemistry, ecology and methods of their teaching, Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University, Uman, Ukraine, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4312-6194>

Zadorozhna O.

candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Chemistry, Ecology and Methods of Teaching Uman State Pedagogical University named after Pavel Tychyna, Uman, Ukraine, ORCID: 0000-0002-5039-017X

ABSTRACT

Chemistry as an academic subject makes the greatest contribution to the formation of the personality of the younger generation through the intellectual sphere of a person. Equipping students with knowledge of chemistry and the chemical industry has always been one of the objectives of teaching chemistry in Ukrainian schools. The revised chemistry curriculum repeatedly emphasizes the importance of equipping students with the knowledge necessary to actively participate in communist construction. It specifies ways to further improve the efficiency of human activity.

However, the development of specific issues cannot replace the creation of an effective methodology for the formation of systemic knowledge of chemistry in general. Therefore, the development of a holistic methodology for the formation of systemic knowledge in chemistry seems quite relevant. It leads to the realization of the principle of the unity of learning, education and development of students as the leading principle of teaching chemistry in Ukrainian schools. Purpose, objectives, object and subject of the study.

Based on the shortcomings of both students' knowledge and the requirements for general chemical education in a developed socialist society, the purpose of this study is to develop a scientifically based holistic methodology for the formation of systematic knowledge of chemistry.

Keywords: formation of the personality of the younger generation chemistry, educational work, principles of chemical production, chemical facts, analysis of results, methodological principles, chemicals and processes, experimental efficiency.

Formulation of the problem. Describing the widespread use of the concept of systematicity in various fields of science and technology, V.G. Afanasiev in the introduction to his book "Systematicity and Society" writes that "nowadays in science, and in practice, one of the most common and fashionable terms is: "system", "systemicity", "systemic approach. Emphasizing the regularity and objective necessity of systematic consideration of all issues of science and practice, he continues: "The successes of modern science and practice convincingly indicate that the world around us, both material and ideal, are not separate, isolated from each other objects, phenomena and processes, but a set of interconnected and interacting objects, a kind of systemic, holistic education" [3, p. 119].

Therefore, more and more often we began to talk about systems in physics and chemistry, biological systems, social systems, etc. The concept of a control system is central to cybernetics. After a short break due to further improvement of the quality of the learning process, the system of students' knowledge in various subjects is once again in the orbit of attention of didactors and methodologists. The analysis and design of systems of various types and the management of natural systems as a promising area of modern research require their own methodological justification and, if possible, an accurate definition of the initial concepts.

The methodological basis for the study and design of any system and its management is the philosophical

principle of systematicity. In its most general form, this principle means that "...the phenomenon of objective reality, viewed from the standpoint of the laws of the systemic whole and the interaction of its constituent parts, forms a special epistemological prism, or a special "measurement" of reality" [4, p. 214].

Systematicity is a property of objective reality, and it depends on what a person thinks about it. The objective connection of objects, processes and phenomena can be noticed or not noticed, taken into account or not taken into account in the course of cognition and practical activity; some connections can be singled out, abstracted from others, and others can be invented by ourselves, "imposed" on the object reality, and neither reality itself nor the objective connections between objects, processes and phenomena that exist in it regardless of our consciousness, systematic or unsystematic thinking will be affected in the least. The epistemological and logical aspects of systematicity are derived from its ontological aspect. F. Engels characterized this circumstance in his *Dialectic of Nature* as follows: "All of the nature available to us forms a kind of system, a kind of aggregate connection of bodies, and here we understand by the word body all material realities, from the star to the atom. The fact that these bodies are in a mutual connection already implies that they influence each other, and it is their mutual influence on each other that is movement itself... This conclusion became inev-

itable as soon as people cognized the universe as a system, as a mutual connection of bodies. In solving the problem of integrating modern scientific and technical knowledge, materialistic dialectics and the philosophical principle of systematicity also prove to be the fundamental basis for the systematic synthesis of knowledge.

Methods of research. To develop systemic knowledge, it is important to give students a holistic view not only of the scientific theory and its structure, but also of each individual element of this theory. Each element of the theory has its own content, and its integrity is also conditioned by structural connections. "The real means of mastering these connections is for students to construct a story in a certain system, so by teaching students to construct a systemic story, we form the necessary connections in their minds. On the other hand, the construction of a story that conveys the integrity of the object of its content indicates the degree of mastery of systemic knowledge. L.Y. Zorina found that in order to develop students' skills to rebuild knowledge as the main conditions for mastering systemic knowledge, it is necessary to include methodological knowledge in the content of general education.

In defining the concept of systematic knowledge, L. Zorina used the method of comparing concepts. This method always contributes to a clearer differentiation of concepts that are close to each other. In order to reveal the essence of the concept of "systematic knowledge", she compares this concept with the concept of "systematic knowledge". In contrast to systematicity, "systematicity is a quality of knowledge that characterizes the presence in the mind of the student of meaningful and logical connections between individual components of knowledge. However, this is not enough for the formation of systemic knowledge, that is, for the realization of structural and functional relationships within a scientific theory" [11, p. 344].

Analysis of recent research and publications.

Based on the presence of integral properties, he divides all systems into summative and integral. The main feature of a summative system is that when components of such a system are included or excluded, neither the system itself nor its other components undergo noticeable qualitative changes: the system only increases or decreases in size. Each of the components of a summative system is autonomous, its change depends only on itself - this is a specific property that is not inherent in all objects and phenomena of reality.

Like all concepts, the concept of an integral system is also relative. There is no absolute boundary between the summative and integral systems. In the course of the development of the material world, as a result of the action of integral forces, summative systems acquire the character of integral systems, and vice versa: as a result of the action of disorganizing forces, integral systems turn into summative systems [5, p. 244].

The concept of connection plays a central role in revealing the essence of the concepts of system and systematicity. Marxist philosophy considers connection as an objective form of being *in se*. Using as a method of defining the concept of connection the fixation of

those features of connection that distinguish it from other types of relations:

1) objectivity of relations between phenomena, their independence from our consciousness means the objectivity of systems;

2) the essentiality of relations between phenomena means that a thing always exists in a system;

3) the diversity of types of relations determines the corresponding diversity of types of systems formed by means of these relations;

4) since any connection is an interconnection, it means that at least two systems can be built on the same substrate, differing from each other in the direction of connections between elements;

5) universality of interconnections implies universality of the system, i.e. any objects can be represented as some systems;

6) the reflexivity of relations means that the system is not obligatory, but implies the dismemberment of the object into elements that are interrelated;'

7) the relative nature of the relationship implies that the concept of system makes sense in contrast to the correlative concept.

A whole is finally formed only when the connections between its elements, as a result of constant interaction with the environment, become stable, when a relatively stable structure of the whole emerges. Structure as a way of connecting elements is an invariant aspect of the system. Establishing the law of relations between elements is the identification of the system's structure, which embodies the characteristic features of a new type of integrity and determines its reproduction in the process of change and development. It is the structure that gives systems the necessary integrity and determines their stable characteristics that allow distinguishing what is called an integral system from objects of a different kind. The integrity of any system and its structure becomes apparent most often only in change and development. A change in the state of one of the subsystems inevitably entails a change in the others [6, p. 245].

An analysis of the philosophical literature shows that there is a more complex relationship between integrity and structure. While the integrity of a system is ensured by its stable structure, the structure of the system, in turn, also depends on the whole. This idea is most consistently expressed in the work of I. B. Blavberg, V. N. Sadovsky and E. G. Yudin. They write that "connection, integrity and the stable structure caused by them are the distinctive features of any system" [7, p. 425].

Results. The concept of structure is related to the concept of element. We can talk about an element only in accordance with a certain way of dividing a system into elements. Other ways of dividing a given system may result in the selection of other entities as the original element. In an organic system, an element is defined by its function, i.e., an element is a minimal unit capable of performing a certain function independently. Since an element acts as a kind of limit of possible division of an object, its own structure is usually not taken

into account when characterizing a system - its constituent elements are no longer considered as components of the system.

Systemicity as an integral property of natural and social systems is reflected in human cognition. The distinction between the qualities of objects that are integral systems and objects that form summative systems is the first systemic moment that is accessible to direct subject knowledge. From the level of direct knowledge, cognition moves to the next, higher level, when a phenomenon is cognized as an element of a knowledge system. The possibilities of cognition remain limited if it does not rise above the level of the direct being of the subject, 'if behind individual phenomena it does not seek to find systems of phenomena: behind individual people - society and the laws of development of socio-economic formations; behind individual representatives of the plant and animal world - biological species and the laws of their evolution; behind individual physical bodies and chemical compounds - the material system of the Earth in the unity of its various levels [8, p. 268].

Any science, including chemistry, is a system of interconnected elements. The elements of a science can be different depending on which aspect of it is considered. B. M. Kedrov distinguishes the following three aspects:

- 1) subject matter, when the object of scientific knowledge itself is studied;
- 2) methodological; when the way in which the truth is cognized is determined;
- 3) subjective-purposeful, when the focus is on the practical goal for which scientific research is being done.

These three aspects of any science answer the three questions posed to the research: what is known, how it is known, and why it is known.

Structure as an invariant, the law of the internal organization of a science, ensures its unity, integrity, and qualities that are specific to that science. Thus, the specificity of chemistry as a science should be sought in the way the elements of chemical science are connected.

A characteristic feature of the modern chemical picture of nature is its systematic nature. Thus, V. S. Vyazovkin considers the chemical picture of nature as a special form of systematization of chemical knowledge, within which the most fundamental provisions of chemistry, other natural sciences and the modern form of materialistic philosophy are synthesized. According to this definition, the chemical picture of nature is broader than chemistry as a science, including, in addition to chemical knowledge, knowledge of the borderline natural sciences and philosophy. On the other hand, the chemical picture of nature is already chemistry, which includes, in addition to scientific knowledge, the methods of obtaining it. Since the chemical picture of nature forms the basis for a style of thinking that is unique to chemistry, the approach to describing, explaining, and predicting chemicals and processes can be systematic.

At present, the systematic nature of chemical

thinking can be traced at three main levels of epistemological analysis: individual material carriers of the chemical form of matter movement, chemical reaction, and technological process. At the first level, the systemic nature of the chemical thinking style requires the researcher to analyze the structure of the object, study its main elements and the relationships between them, and take into account the interaction of this object with the environment. The results of such an analysis are conclusions about the non-identity of the same chemical element in the 'free' state and as part of a chemical compound, about the inequality of chemical bonds between single chemical elements in different compounds [9, p. 214].

The systematic style of chemical thinking is based on the inviolability of the properties of the chemical whole to the properties of its parts and the limited use of the principle of additivity in describing the properties of the whole. The nucleus of an atom, an atom, a molecule, and a molecular orbital are integral systems. Each of them has a new quality that is not reducible to the properties or the sum of the properties of its constituent parts, as well as certain features that are not inherent in its constituent components. A water molecule is composed of hydrogen and oxygen atoms, but it shares other properties with all the others. The properties of the same substance in different aggregate states differ from each other because the nature and manner of organizing the bonds between the constituent parts of the substance also differ from each other.

The systemic nature of the style of chemical thinking at the level of a chemical reaction implies that the chemical process is considered not as a simple interaction of reacting substances, but as an integral kinetic system. The empirical and theoretical regularities of a chemical process should be studied as a result of the interaction and mutual influence of all components of the chemical reaction - starting materials, intermediate compounds, transition states, impurities, catalyst, final products, etc. The systematic nature of our understanding of a chemical reaction can only be achieved by accurately determining the place of each of the above-mentioned components of a chemical process in a given kinetic system.

The systematic nature of cognition at the level of technological process requires consideration of any chemical production process as a set of different chemical reactions and means of their practical implementation in industrial conditions.

Analyzing the transition from the objectively existing systematicity to the systematicity of modern chemical cognition, V.S. Vyazovkin identifies the following logical chain: "systematic objective process - systematic methodological approach - systematic theory". Since the knowledge of the younger generation in chemistry should correspond to the state and structure of chemical science, this chain should be supplemented by another link - the systematicity of students' knowledge of chemistry [10, p. 199].

Conclusions. Thus, the emergence of the structure of concepts in the students' knowledge system is due to the holistic teaching methodology, mainly the construction of educational material. In the other experimental

and control classes, the structure of concepts in the students' knowledge system was not formed.

Factor analysis of the results of the pedagogical experiment showed that all the factors found describe well the level of pupils' knowledge on the topic "Solutions. Water. Bases". The factor of establishing connections on the knowledge of pupils in the control classes is absent at all. At the same time, in the first experimental classes, it determines 86% of all pupils. The factor of inability to make connections characterizes only 2% of pupils in the first experimental classes. In the knowledge of pupils in control classes, this factor ranks first, describing 74% of pupils. A very high numerical value in the control classes is the factor of random response, which characterizes 61% of students in these classes. This means that they answered the questions "is water with its most characteristic properties suitable for drinking" and "do two solutions containing different amounts of solute have the same concentration" quite randomly "no, it is not. In most cases, they did not have a corresponding justification.

The highest values in the experimental classes are also attributed to the factor of conceptualization, which describes about half of the pupils.

Regression analysis of the data of the pedagogical experiment on the topic "Solutions. Water. Bases" according to the first version of the test showed that 50% of pupils who studied this topic according to the holistic methodology received at least 8.92 points out of 10 possible. Since the regression equation describing the acquisition of systemic knowledge by pupils in the first experimental classes does not include linking as an argument, this methodology fully ensures the establishment of links in the teaching material.

All the connections that exist in this educational material. The textbook text has a greater impact on the knowledge of students in control classes. Those concepts whose connections are presented in the textbook appear more often together than others. Therefore, the Pearson correlation coefficients of such pairs of concepts have higher numerical values. Conversely, for those pairs of concepts between which there are only so-called loose connections, these coefficients have the lowest values. The values of Pearson's correlation coefficients between pairs of concepts in the textbook, in turn, correlate with the number of connections established by students, which shows the influence of the textbook. Students in the control classes were much worse at establishing connections between those pairs of concepts with low Pearson's correlation values.

The results of the pedagogical experiment on the interconnected study of the structure of the atom and the periodic table of chemical elements reveal the same trends that were observed in the formation of systemic knowledge in grade 7. The construction of educational material on the basis of the principle of compactness and continuity, along with the cross-cutting solution of

relevant tasks and exercises, helps to establish connections in the educational material, and students in experimental classes make fewer mistakes in establishing connections. Due to the strong mastery of connections, students of experimental classes are better able to reveal the physical essence of the periodic system, apply their theoretical knowledge in practice [14, p. 215].

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